

Pword-report

- Language name: **Vietnamese (LID 494).**
 Name: René Schiering (University of Leipzig).
 Sources: Dinh-Hoa, Nguyen 1997. *Vietnamese. Tieng viet khong son phan.* (London Oriental and African Language Library, 9). Amsterdam Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
 Emeneau, M. B. 1951. *Studies in Vietnamese (Annamese) Grammar.* (University of California Publications in Linguistics, 8). Berkeley/Los Angeles: University of California Press.
 Nhàn, Ngo Thanh 1984. *The syllabeme and patterns of word formation in Vietnamese.* PhD-Dissertation, NYU.
 Noyer, Rolf 1998. "Vietnamese 'Morphology' and the Definition of Word." *University of Pennsylvania Working Papers in Linguistics* 5: 65-89.
 Pham, Hoa 2000. "Vietnamese reduplication: phonetics-phonology mismatch of tones." In: Jensen, John & Gerard Van Herk (eds.). *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Canadian Linguistics Association 1999.* Ottawa: Cahiers Linguistiques d'Ottawa: 225-236.
 Pham, Andrea H. 2003. *Vietnamese Tone: A New Analysis.* (Outstanding Dissertations in Linguistics). New York & London: Routledge.
 Thomas, David D. 1962. "On defining the 'word' in Vietnamese." *Van-Hoa Nguyet-San* 11: 519-523.
 Thompson, Laurence C. 1963. "The Problem of the Word in Vietnamese." *Word* 19: 39-52.
 Thompson, Laurence C. 1965. *A Vietnamese Grammar.* Seattle: University of Washington Press.
 Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com, 09/14/2007.
 Date completed: 12/06/2007.

I Language Profile

- # of speakers: 67,439,139 (65,795,718 in Viet Nam).
 Spoken in: Viet Nam, Cambodia, China, Laos, Thailand.
 Contact languages: Chinese, French.
 Status: Official language. Literacy rate in first language: 65%. Literacy rate in second language: 80%.
 Prospects: Maintenance.
 Structural results: Lexical and structural borrowing: Chinese and French loans, Sino-Vietnamese compounds.

II Morpheme Types

1. Stem

2. Restricted pre-posed formative

IVC + verb ‘emphatic’

- (1) a. *lò-mò* ‘grope feverishly’
 b. *lun-vun* ‘be in very small pieces’ (Thompson 1965: 158)

3. Restricted post-posed formative

verb + *Cang* ‘emphatic’

- (2) a. *dễ-dàng* ‘be very easy’
 b. *cũ-càng* ‘be very old’ (Thompson 1965: 161)

4. Unrestricted pre-posed formative

Clause-initial particle *à* ‘new topic’

- (3) *à* *ông* *đẽ* *xây* *gì* *đó*
 NEW.TOPIC gentleman put turn whatever there
 ‘What have you put on there?’ (Thompson 1965: 259)

5. Unrestricted post-posed formative

Clause-final particle *à* ‘mild surprise’

- (4) *không đi* *à*
 NEG go MILD.SURPRISE
 ‘Oh, you’re not going?’ (Thompson 1965: 260)

III Syllable

Syllable structure

The canonical syllable structure for Vietnamese is schematized in (5).

- (5) The syllable in Vietnamese

Tone	
Initial	Rhyme
C	(w)V(C)

The obligatory onset consonant slot cannot be filled by the bilabial voiceless stop /p/. The rhyme obligatorily consists of a vocalic nucleus, which is filled by either a short, long or diphthongal vowel, i.e. /i, u, e, ɤ, ɤ:, o, ɛ, a, a:, ɔ, iɤ, uɤ, uɤ:/. The glide /w/ may optionally precede the nucleus. The coda position can optionally be filled by one of the eight segments /p, t, k, m, n, ŋ, y, w/. The phonetic realization of the final velar consonants /k, ŋ/ is determined by the quantity and quality of the preceding vowel. After the short, round vowels /u, o, ɔ/, the two consonants surface in their labio-velar allophones, i.e. [k^p] and [ŋ^m], respectively. If the preceding vowel is short and front, they are realized as the palatals [c] and [ɲ], respectively (Pham 2003:138).

Monosyllabic words

The data in (6) provide examples for the varying degrees of syllable complexity evidenced in monosyllabic words.

- (6) a. *đi* /di/ ‘go’
 b. *noạ* /nwa:/ ‘lazy’
 c. *bay* /bay/ ‘fly’
 d. *ngoài* /ŋwà:y/ ‘outside’ (Nhàn 1984)

The minimal word *đi* /di/ ‘go’ in (6a) also constitutes a minimal pause group. It exhibits a simple CV structure and contains a short vowel as its nucleus.

Vowel-initial words

According to the syllable structure in (5), the onset consonant is obligatory, i.e. there are no vowel-initial words. Words which are presented as vowel-initial in writing are actually realized with a glottal stop onset.

Polysyllabic words

Monomorphemic and morphologically complex polysyllabic words are composed of the syllable types summarized in (5). Monomorphemic words are most commonly monosyllabic. The few polysyllabic monomorphemic words are place names, e.g. *Sài-gòn* and *Thủ-dầu-một*, or loans, such as the French borrowings *va-li* ‘suitcase’ and *com-mi-nít* ‘communist’ or the English borrowing *a-me-ri-ca* ‘America’. Polymorphemic words which are derived by either reduplication or compounding, on the other hand, are generally polysyllabic. Within such words, no word-related phonotactic restrictions or variations across lexical categories are reported. The examples in (7) illustrate this point for prefixing and suffixing reduplication (bases underlined).

- (7) a. *lờ-mờ* /lɣ: mɣ:/ ‘very dim’
 b. *toè-loe* /twè: lwe:/ ‘bell-mouthed’
 c. *bây-nhây* /bɣy nɣy/ ‘very sleazy’
 d. *chúénh-choáng* /cwéŋ cwá:ŋ/ ‘be tipsy-turvy’
 e. *tàn tạ* /tàn tạ/ ‘worn out’
 f. *quăn queo* /kwatun kwew/ ‘very curly, twisted’
 g. *mơ-màng* /mɣ: mà:ŋ/ ‘dreaming’
 h. *cong-queo* /kɔŋ kwew/ ‘badly twisted’ (Nhàn 1984)

Nhàn (1984: 82-83) reports a general tendency to reduce complex /Cw/-clusters in the weakly stressed syllable of reduplicative words, cf. *toè-loe* [twè: lwe:] ~ [tè: lwe:] ‘bell-mouthed’. Accordingly, consonant clusters could be said to be disfavored in the initial syllable of polysyllabic words.

Superheavy syllables

Superheavy syllables are attested for words with a long vowel or a diphthong in nucleus position and a coda consonant, e.g. *ngoài* /ŋwà:y/ ‘outside’. In morphologically complex polysyllabic forms, such syllables are possible in every position of the word, cf. the data in (7). (See also Pham 2003: 140-150 for the significance of the rhyme in tonal phonology.)

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

The tonal distinctions summarized in (8) are contrastive in Vietnamese.

(8) Vietnamese tones (Pham 2003: 10)

high	<i>ngang</i> (high level)	<i>sắc</i> (high rising)	<i>ngã</i> (creaky rising)
low	<i>huyền</i> (low level)	<i>nặng</i> (creaky falling)	<i>hỏi</i> (low rising)

With respect to *sắc* and *nặng*, these tones have short allotones (called *sắc2* and *nặng2*, respectively) whose distribution is restricted to syllables which are closed by a stop consonant. The data in (9) gives examples for each of the eight surface tones.

- (9)
- | | | |
|---------------------------|---------|------------------|
| a. <i>mau</i> ‘fast’ | (ngang) | |
| b. <i>láu</i> ‘clever’ | (sắc) | |
| c. <i>vất</i> ‘laborious’ | (sắc2) | |
| d. <i>mỡ</i> ‘greasy’ | (ngã) | |
| e. <i>tàn</i> ‘worn out’ | (huyền) | |
| f. <i>lạnh</i> ‘cold’ | (nặng) | |
| g. <i>ngặt</i> ‘severe’ | (nặng2) | |
| h. <i>đỏ</i> ‘red’ | (hỏi) | (Pham 2000: 228) |

In running speech, the realization of tones is stable, i.e. there are no tonal sandhi rules which operate on phrasal or sentential levels (see Pham 2003: 3). However, there are several patterns of reduplication in Vietnamese which are associated with special tonal phonology (see IX).

Stress

According to Thompson (1965: 106-107), each syllable in Vietnamese is accompanied by one stress. Monomorphemic, disyllabic words are realized with final stress if uttered in isolation, e.g. *va-¹li* ‘suitcase’. At higher levels of prosodic structure, three levels of stress may be distinguished: weak, medium and heavy stress. The general pattern is that of iambic phrasing, but ultimately the degree of stress on the syllables within a pause group is determined by the information load of the different elements. For stress assignment in compounds, reduplication and phrases see VIII, IX and X, respectively.

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

In general, every morpheme of the language constitutes a syllable. Sub-syllabic morphemes are only instanced in the paradigm of deictic elements given in (10). In these forms, initial and rhyme could be analyzed as separate morphemes, e.g. *đây* ‘here’: *đ-* ‘relative location’ + *-ây* ‘near speaker’ (Thompson 1963: 43, Thompson 1965: 106).

(10) Deictic elements in Vietnamese (Thompson 1963: 43)

<i>đâu</i> ‘anywhere, wherever’	<i>đây</i> ‘here’	<i>đấy</i> ‘there’
<i>nào</i> ‘any, whichever’	<i>này</i> ‘this’	<i>no</i> ‘another, that’
<i>bao</i> ‘to whatever extent’	<i>bây</i> ‘to this extent’	<i>bấy</i> ‘to that extent’
<i>sao</i> ‘however, in whatever way’	<i>vây</i> ‘this way, thus’	<i>vấy</i> ‘that way, so’

Notice: © 2007 Autotyp. All data from these reports must include citations for both the primary reference source(s) and the authors of the reports.

VI “Free” Grammatical Morphemes

Clitics

Enclitics undergo substantial reduction in running speech, such that all segments of the clitic are deleted but its tone remains. If the clitic attaches to an obstruents-final host, the tone is realized on a homorganic nasal, if it attaches to a vowel- or glide-final host, the tone is realized on the lengthened vowel or glide, respectively (Pham 2003: 33-34).

- (11) Clitic reduction in Vietnamese (Pham 2003: 33)
- a. [xʰn là:m] → [xʰñ] (pray do)
 - b. [cɔ nɔ̃] → [cɔ̃] (let he)

VII Polymorphemic Stem Forms

Except for the phonotactic process of cluster reduction (see III), the special patterns of tonal phonology in reduplication (see IX), and the exceptional stress pattern of Sino-Vietnamese compounds (VIII), all morphemes participate in the same ways in the phonological processes of the language.

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Compounds

In Vietnamese, several patterns of compounding can be distinguished: syntactic vs. non-syntactic and coordinative vs. adjunctive. The data in (12) present one example for each type.

- (12) Types of compounds in Vietnamese (Thompson 1965: 126ff.)

	syntactic	non-syntactic
coordinative	<i>bàn-ghế</i> ‘furniture’ (<i>bàn</i> ‘table’ + <i>ghế</i> ‘chair’) ~ <i>bàn ghế</i> ‘tables and chairs’	<i>sợ-hoảng</i> ‘be terrified’ (<i>sợ</i> ‘be afraid’ + <i>hoảng</i> ‘be panic stricken’)
adjunctive	<i>người ở</i> ‘servant’ (<i>người</i> ‘person’ + <i>ở</i> ‘be located’) ~ <i>người ở</i> ‘person residing’	<i>học trò</i> ‘schoolchild, pupil’ (<i>học</i> ‘to study’ + <i>trò</i> ‘school-age child’)

In terms of their prosodic behavior, compound words are composed of syllables adhering to the syllable template in (5) and carrying one of the six tones in (8). Stress assignment in compounds is illustrated in (13).

- (13)
- a. *người* ¹*ta* ‘somebody’
 - b. *một* ¹*mình* ‘alone’
 - c. *hoa* ¹*hồng* ‘rose’
 - d. *Liên*-¹*hiệp quốc* ‘United nations’

In the default case, disyllabic compound words are realized with final stress. In (13d), the pseudo-compound has its origin in structural borrowing from Chinese. In such Sino-Vietnamese compounds, stress is assigned to the left branch of the construction, in which stress is realized on the final syllable.

IX Reduplication

Reduplication expresses a number of meanings, such as distributive, iterative, attenuative, intensive and emphatic (see Thompson 1965: 139ff., Noyer 1998: 80f. for a summary). The various reduplicative patterns with prefixed and suffixed reduplicants are summarized in (14) (bases underlined). Only complete reduplication is fully productive.

(14) Patterns of reduplication in Vietnamese (Thompson 1965: 139f.)

	prefixed	suffixed
alliterative	<i>la-lét</i> ‘do with much pain’	<i>rô-rệt</i> ‘be very clear’
riming	<i>bối-rối</i> ‘be uneasy, troubled’	<i>khóc-lóc</i> ‘cry, whimper’
vocalic	<i>léu-láo</i> ‘be ill-mannered’	<i>mập-mạp</i> ‘be fat, chubby’
tonal	<i>bự-bự</i> ‘be very big’	<i>đen đen</i> ‘be rather black’
complete	<i>noi noi</i> ‘keep talking and talking’ (noi ‘talk’) <i>sạch sạch</i> ‘be rather clean’ (sạch ‘be clean’)	

The various types of reduplication differ with respect to how much of the base is copied into the prefixed or suffixed reduplicant. In alliterative reduplication, only the onset of the base is copied whereas the rime of both base and reduplicant are identical in riming reduplication. In some cases the tone of the reduplicant changes in the process. In vocalic reduplications, everything except for the vowel is repeated in the reduplicant. In tonal reduplication everything except for the tone is retained in the reduplicant. Finally, since both members of complete reduplications are entirely identical, we cannot decide whether the reduplicant is prefixed or suffixed in disyllabic forms.

Disyllabic reduplications as in (15a) exhibit final stress. Longer polysyllabic reduplicative strings are parsed as two stress units with final stress, cf. (15b).

- (15) a. *nói 'nói* ‘keep talking and talking’
b. *mơ 'mơ màng 'màng* ‘deep in the state of dreaming’

Apart from the segmental resemblances between the base and its reduplicant, some reduplications also exhibit special tonal phonology, such that the base and the reduplicant carry a tone of the same tone register. The data in (16) illustrate this point for each of the eight phonetic tones of Vietnamese.

(16) *Tone in Vietnamese reduplication* (Pham 2000: 228)

a. <i>mau</i> ‘fast’	→	<i>mau mắn</i> ‘very fast’	(ngang - sắc)
b. <i>láu</i> ‘clever’	→	<i>láu linh</i> ‘very clever’	(sắc - hỏi)
c. <i>vất</i> ‘laborious’	→	<i>vất vả</i> ‘very hard’	(sắc2 - hỏi)
d. <i>mỡ</i> ‘greasy’	→	<i>mỡ màng</i> ‘very greasy’	(ngã - huyền)
e. <i>tàn</i> ‘worn out’	→	<i>tàn tạ</i> ‘very worn out’	(huyền - nặng)
f. <i>lạnh</i> ‘cold’	→	<i>lạnh lẽo</i> ‘very cold’	(nặng - ngã)
g. <i>ngặt</i> ‘severe’	→	<i>ngặt nghèo</i> ‘very hard’	(nặng2 - huyền)
h. <i>đỏ</i> ‘red’	→	<i>đỏ đàn</i> ‘very red’	(hỏi - ngang)

The examples in (16a-d) show reduplications of bases with high tones. The bases in the reduplications in (16e-h) carry low tones. The tone of the suffixed reduplicant is never identical to the one of the base. However, the tone of the reduplicant belongs to the same tone register. Note that *ngã*, which is traditionally classified as a high tone, patterns with low tones (16d) and (16f), whereas *hỏi*, which is traditionally classified as a low tone, patterns with high

tones in (16b), (16c) and (16h). The register membership of the *ngã* and *hỏi* tones is thus reversed for the sake of the tonal phonology of reduplication, cf. Concave Tone Reversal (Nhàn 1984: 78) or Flip-Flip-Rule (Pham 2001).

Tone register harmony is not fully productive, such that we find exceptions like *cứng-cứng* ‘very hard’, combining a high and a low tone. In this case of tone register dissimilation (Thompson 1965: 155-157), the high tone *sắc* is combined with the low tone *nặng*.

X Phrase/Sentence-level Phenomena

Phrases

At the phrase level, the default placement of heavy stress is on the final syllable. Accordingly, the phrases in (17) are realized with final stress.

- (17) a. *hoa* 'hông ‘pink flower’
 b. *Tôi không* 'biết. ‘I don’t know’

The phonological phrases of running speech is illustrated with the utterance in (18).

- (18) Phonological phrasing in Vietnamese (Thompson 1965: 107)
 ('Nói) (phải 'có người) (nói 'đi) (nói 'lại) (chớ 'bắt)
 speak ought exist person speak go speak come prohibit constrain
 (người ta 'nói) (một mình 'hoài)!
 someone speak alone continually
 ‘For a conversation, [you] ought to have people talking back and forth, not make somebody talk alone all the time!’

The seven stress units vary in phonological length from monosyllabic to trisyllabic. The first unit consists of a monosyllabic lexical unit only, whereas the second one is made up of three syllables. Although final stress is the default, the placement of heavy stress within a stress unit is ultimately governed by the semantic saliency of the elements within the structure. This principle accounts for the non-final stress in the second stress unit of the utterance, in which the head *có* ‘exist’ receives heavy stress in penultimate position of the phrase. Note also the lack of heavy stress on the final syllable of the compound *người ta* ‘someone’.

Clauses/Sentences

The utterance in (19) exemplifies the demarcation of intonational phrases and utterances by intonation contours.

- (19) Intonation in Vietnamese (Thompson 1965: 108)
 (*Tôi* 'đến *nha*), (*má* 'tôi) (*mở* *cửa* 'ra), (*tôi* 'vô).
 I arrive house, mother I open door exit, I enter.
 ‘I arrived at the house, my mother opened the door, and I went in.’

The utterance in (19) comprises of three intonational phrases and four phonological phrases. The first intonational phrase is coextensive with the first phonological phrase. The comma indicates the realization of falling intonation on the final part of the phrase, which primarily signals the speaker’s intention to continue. The second intonation phrase, which is again delimited by falling intonation, encompasses two phonological phrases with regular final

heavy stress. The final syllable of the third intonational phrase is at the same time the final syllable of the utterance. The period represents the realization of fading intonation at the end of this utterance, which signals that the speaker assumes a certain result of his speech and allows the hearer to take his turn. In terms of prosodic domains, decreasing intonation can be viewed as a property of the intonational phrase, which maps onto syntactic units potentially containing more than one phrase, i.e. clauses. Terminal intonation, of which fading intonation is only one type, closes the phonological utterance which relates to the sentence.

XI Other Special Things to Look for

[Not reported]